

COMPOSITION AND TURNOVER TIME OF ORGANIC MATTER IN SOIL FRACTIONS WITH DIFFERENT MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY

TOMMASO CHITI^{1,2}, GIACOMO CERTINI³, FABIO MARZAIOLI⁴, LUIGI PAOLO D'ACQUI⁵,
CLAUDIA FORTE⁶, SIMONA CASTALDI^{2,7,8}, RICCARDO VALENTINI^{1,2,8}

¹*Department for Innovation in Biological, Agro-food and Forest Systems (DIBAF), University of Tuscany, via San C. De Lellis snc, 01100 Viterbo, Italy.*

²*Foundation Euro-Mediterranean Center on Climate Change (CMCC), Division on Impacts on Agriculture, Forests and Ecosystem Services (IAFES), viale Trieste 127, 01100 Viterbo Italy.*

³*Dipartimento di Scienze e Tecnologie Agrarie, Alimentari, Ambientali e Forestali (DAGRI), Università di Firenze, p.le delle Cascine 28, 50144 Firenze, Italy.*

⁴*Dipartimento di Matematica e Fisica, Università degli Studi della Campania Luigi Vanvitelli, viale Lincoln 5, 81100 Caserta, Italy.*

⁵*Istituto di Ricerca sugli Ecosistemi Terrestri (IRET), CNR, via Madonna del Piano 10, 50019 Sesto Fiorentino, Italy.*

⁶*Istituto di Chimica dei Composti Organometallici (ICCOM), CNR, via G. Moruzzi 1, 56124 Pisa, Italy.*

⁷*Dipartimento di Scienze e Tecnologie Ambientali, Biologiche e Farmaceutiche (DISTABIF), Università degli Studi della Campania Luigi Vanvitelli, via Vivaldi 43, 81100 Caserta, Italy.*

⁸*RUDN University, Moscow, Russia*

*Corresponding author: Phone +39 0761 357251, Fax: +39 0761 357389

E-mail: tommaso.chiti@unitus.it

Abstract

The composition and turnover time (TT) of organic matter in soil fractions with different magnetic susceptibility were studied in a tropical primary forest in Ghana. The starting hypothesis was that soil organic matter (SOM) composition and properties depend on the magnetic susceptibility of the minerals SOM is associated with. Soil samples from 0-5, 5-15, 15-30, and 30-50 cm depth intervals were sieved to remove rock fragments (> 2.0 mm) and then separated into two size fractions (0.5-2.0 mm and <0.5 mm) that were processed by a High Gradient Magnetic Separator (HGMS) to finally obtain four fractions with different size and/or magnetic susceptibility. All fractions were analysed for their mineral composition, ^{14}C concentration, and spectroscopic properties of SOM (^{13}C CPMAS NMR).

From a mineralogical point of view, the magnetic (MA) fractions essentially differed from the non-magnetic (NM) ones for a higher presence of oxides and kaolinite, which *per se* is non-magnetic. In terms of chemical composition of SOM, the MA fractions showed higher contribution of labile compounds than the NM ones. At all depths, the ^{14}C concentration revealed shortest TT of SOM in the <0.5 mm MA fraction and longest TT in the <0.5 mm NM fraction, while the 0.5-2.0 mm fractions showed intermediate and similar TT's. At depths <5 cm, the fine NM fraction was not significantly influenced by the carbon fixed after the 1950's ("bomb carbon"), having TT of almost 1000 years and suggesting that in this tropical soil some SOM can be stabilized also in relatively superficial horizons.

Our findings support the hypothesis that minerals are driving factors of the fate of SOM. As a consequence, soil fractionation based on magnetic susceptibility might be a meaningful procedure for having insight into SOM dynamics.

1. Introduction

Tropical forests are a critical component of the global carbon (C) cycle and their response to environmental changes will play a key role in driving future concentrations of carbon dioxide (CO₂) in the atmosphere (Grace et al. 2014; Valentini et al. 2014). Presently, in tropical regions much attention is devoted to determine soil organic matter (SOM) losses induced by deforestation (Achard et al., 2014; Chiti et al., 2014), forest degradation (Chiti et al., 2018; Miles and Kapos, 2008; Vaglio Laurin et al., 2016), and forest management (Berenguer et al., 2014; Chiti et al., 2016). Paradoxically, little investigation deals with the knowledge of SOM dynamics in relatively undisturbed primary forests (Chiti et al., 2010; Saner et al. 2012). Organic matter in soil is protected from mineralization by a variety of factors, of both physical and chemical nature, which altogether lead to the occurrence of SOM pools with different turnover times (TT) (Han et al., 2016; Torn et al., 1997). In the last decades, the tracing of radiocarbon (¹⁴C) throughout terrestrial ecosystems has emerged as a crucial technique in studying the global C cycle (Trumbore, 2009). The method relies on the sudden increases, in the 1950s and 1960s, of the ¹⁴C concentration in the atmosphere – the so-called “bomb spike” – induced by nuclear weapon tests (Certini et al., 2013). Atmospheric ¹⁴C is fixed in plant tissues via photosynthesis and finally arrives to soil as plant depositions. This process enabled the development of various models that use “bomb C” as a marker for estimating the natural turnover of organic samples (Gaudinski et al., 2000; Torn, 2009). Research on ¹⁴C concentration in SOM is ample (*e.g.*, Chiti et al., 2011, 2016; McFarlane et al., 2013; Trumbore, 2009).

Bulk SOM fractionation methods aim at obtaining SOM pools with specific properties. Despite the numerous studies on the subject (reviewed by von Lützow et al., 2007), no highly selective methodology for the separation of SOM pools with different TT is yet available. SOM fractionation is often carried out on the basis of solubility (Kaiser and Ellerbrock, 2005), density (Throop et al., 2013), or molecular weight (Certini et al., 2004), although often no correlation between SOM features and TT is observed. A little investigated type of SOM fractionation is that based on

magnetic susceptibility (MS) of minerals, namely High Gradient Magnetic Separation (HGMS), as described by Russell et al. (1984), Shang and Tiessen (1997, 2000) and von Lützow et al. (2007). Compared to chemical treatments, this fractionation procedure has the great advantage of not causing any alteration of SOM. Indeed, MS may have some influence on SOM associated to different mineral fractions. In a volcanic soil of Italy, Wilson et al. (2008) observed that magnetic susceptible ferromagnesian minerals (biotite and orthopyroxene) were much more intensively colonized by fungi than magnetic non-susceptible K-feldspar and glass, although the overall composition of the microbial communities living on the two classes of minerals was similar. Fassbinder et al. (1990) demonstrated the occurrence in soil of “magnetic” bacteria, i.e. bacteria containing magnetite crystals, whose function is difficult to infer. Bulk soil MS generally increases with increasing weathering (Preetz et al., 2017; Singer and Fine, 1989), chiefly because of formation of Fe oxides, which have high affinity for SOM (Colombo et al., 2017; Kaiser et al., 2002). Tropical soils are often highly altered soils rich in oxides, which dominate the mineral composition along with quartz (Tardy, 1997). Despite many oxides are not magnetic (e.g. Al oxides), several others such as the lithogenic magnetite (Fe_3O_4) and titano-magnetite ($\text{Fe}_{3-x}\text{Ti}_x\text{O}_4$) or the pedogenic maghemite (Fe_2O_3 , $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$) are magnetic and may extend their MS to the non-magnetic minerals they are encrusted on (Igel et al., 2012). In this context, isolation of the organic matter associated with the magnetic fraction of soil could represent a promising strategy for investigating SOM dynamics, particularly if the isolated fractions show different TT's. As far as we know, in the scientific literature there are no studies focused on SOM dynamics associated with soil fractions having different MS.

We hypothesised that different SOM pools are associated with mineral fractions having a different MS. To test this hypothesis, we applied HGMS to a soil from a tropical primary forest of Ghana. The obtained soil fractions were investigated by X-ray diffractometry (XRD) and selective dissolutions to have an insight on their mineralogical assemblage and by nuclear magnetic

resonance (NMR) and accelerator mass spectroscopy (AMS) to assess the chemical structure of SOM and its turnover time (TT), respectively.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Study site and sampling

The study site is a primary rainforest located within the Ankasa Wildlife Reserve (5°17'49"N, 2°23'17"W), Western Ghana. The mean annual temperature of the area is about 25 °C and the mean annual precipitation is about 1700 mm, mainly concentrated from March to mid-July and from September to November, with a relatively dry period from December to February. The vegetation is a mixture of evergreen and deciduous species and is typical in the highest rainfall zone in Ghana. The landscape consists of a patchwork of hills with average elevation of 90 m. Soils are strongly weathered and very acid with pH of about 4.0. The investigated soil, which developed on top of a hill over granite of the Cape Coast complex (Ahn, 1961), has a sandy-clay texture and is classified as a Typic Hapludox according to the Soil Taxonomy (Soil Survey Staff, 2014). A detailed description of the vegetation along with a soil profile description can be found in Chiti et al. (2010). We focused on the upper 50 cm of soil, since a previous study performed at the same site (Chiti et al., 2010) revealed that this was the only soil compartment significantly affected by “bomb C” (C fixed since the 1950's), hence the only compartment where short to medium term C dynamics are actually occurring.

Within a 1-ha plot three soil trenches were opened and soil samples were collected from the 0-5, 5-15, 15-30, and 30-50 cm depth intervals. The first interval corresponded to the A horizon, while the deeper intervals were included in the Bo1 horizon (see soil description in Chiti et al., 2010). Soil was sampled at the opposite sides of each trench – so as to have six samples per depth interval – by using a steel cylinder (diameter = 5 cm; height = 5 cm). The same cylinder was used to collect the same number of samples from each layer for bulk density determination. All samples were oven-dried (60 °C) to constant mass, except those for bulk density which were oven-dried at 105 °C until

constant mass, and then passed through a 2 mm mesh size sieve. The analyses were performed on the <2 mm fraction. Total C was measured by dry combustion (ThermoFinnigan Flash EA112 CHN, Okehampton, UK), and corresponded to organic C given that the presence of carbonates in this extremely acid soil is very unlikely.

2.2 High Gradient Magnetic Separation

Three composite samples per depth interval were prepared by combining equal aliquots of the two samples from the opposite sides of each of the three soil profiles. Twenty grams of each composite sample were passed through a 0.5 mm mesh sieve to obtain two size fractions, one <0.5 mm and another comprised between 0.5 mm and 2.0 mm, both of which underwent HGMS by a Frantz Isodynamic Separator (Model L-1, SG Frantz Co, Inc, Trenton, New Jersey, USA). Splitting the fine earth in two size fractions was necessary to avoid continuous jamming of the instrument. The 0.5 mm threshold was selected to have two size classes quite similar on a weight basis. The separator consists of a strong electro-magnet, with a power intensity ranging from 0 to 2 Ampere (A), and a vibrating shoot that can be variably inclined on the horizontal axis. The sample moves down the shoot due to gravity and the magnetic susceptible components are deflected by the transversal magnetic field. At the end of the shoot, magnetic and non-magnetic particles are collected in separate containers (Fig. S1). The higher the shoot inclination, the stronger is the magnetic field required to attract a given magnetic particle. Preliminary trials showed that applying intensities higher than 1 A do not result in any significant increase in the amount of the magnetic fractions (Fig. S2). Therefore, the current intensity was set to 1 A, while the shoot inclination was set to 5°. The fractions obtained from the first run were processed a second time to attain a more selective separation. Overall, four soil fractions per depth interval were obtained: one fraction strongly susceptible to magnetism (hereafter called "magnetic", MA) and one weakly susceptible to magnetism (hereafter called "non-magnetic", NM) for each of two size fractions (<0.5 mm and 0.5-2.0 mm). The four soil fractions per depth interval were weighed and pulverised by a ball mill for

the following analyses: X-ray diffractometry (XRD) selective dissolution, total C, ^{13}C NMR spectroscopy and ^{14}C concentration measurements.

2.3 X-ray diffractometry and selective dissolution

The XRD investigation was conducted on randomly-oriented powders of bulk soil and fractionated material from each depth interval by a Philips PW3830 X-ray diffractometer with $\text{CoK}\alpha$ radiation, 0.02° step size, and 1s step time each point over a 2θ range of $5\text{-}75^\circ$. The identification of the main clay minerals was performed on an oriented clay-size ($<2\ \mu\text{m}$) fraction obtained from a water suspension of the bulk sample from the 30-50 cm layer, where the clay mineral peaks of the bulk soil spectra appeared most distinct. A semi-quantitative analysis of kaolinite (the main clay mineral) was performed in the soil fractions by the Reference Intensity Ratio (RIR) method (Brindley and Brown, 1980). RIR values were based on the relative net peak height ratio of the strongest lines of corundum and the sample measured under the same conditions. For this estimation the spectra were recorded as described above but using a $\text{CuK}\alpha$ anode, because the RIR's reference database used for the calculation referred to copper radiation. Mass percentage of each identified phase was calculated by the X'Pert HighScore program (Philips Analytical, The Netherlands).

Selective dissolutions by dithionite–citrate–bicarbonate (DCB) and acid ammonium oxalate were carried out to determine the crystalline and non-crystalline forms of “free” iron. We used the DCB method as described in Mehra and Jackson (1960), which is potentially able to extract all free iron, provided that the sample is finely ground (McKeague and Day, 1966). Acid ammonium oxalate was used according to Blakemore et al. (1987) to extract the Fe belonging to non-crystalline, short-range order, and amorphous oxides, such as ferrihydrite and ferrihydrite-like minerals, as well as the soluble Fe, exchangeable Fe, and a minor part of Fe bound to organic matter or contained in crystalline oxides and clay minerals. In regard to crystalline oxides, magnetite and maghemite – which are the main contributors of soil MS – are partly dissolved by acid oxalate, opposite to goethite and hematite, which are virtually insoluble (van Oorschot and Dekkers, 2001). Iron in the

extracts was measured by a Horiba Jobin Yvon ULTIMA 2 ICP OES spectrometer.

2.4 ^{13}C NMR spectroscopy

The chemical structure of SOM in the soil fractions was examined by ^{13}C solid-state NMR spectroscopy using cross polarization with magic angle spinning (CP/MAS). Prior to analysis, the samples were treated with 2% HF according to Skjemstad et al. (1994) to remove paramagnetic substances, typically present in the mineral phase, which cause signal loss. The C concentration of the treated samples was measured to determine the treatment-induced C loss. The NMR spectra of the four fractions for each depth were recorded on a Bruker AMX 300-WB spectrometer equipped with a 4 mm CP/MAS probe. The operating frequencies were 300.1 and 75.5 MHz for ^1H and ^{13}C , respectively; the $\pi/2$ pulse was 4 μs on the ^1H channel, the contact time 2 ms and the relaxation delay 4 s. The experimental parameters were chosen on the basis of preliminary experiments. The MAS speed was set to 8 kHz and the number of scans recorded for each sample ranged between 20,000 and 40,000, depending on the sample. Seven chemical-shift regions of the spectra, corresponding to the main C forms, were integrated and expressed as per cent contribution to the total area under the spectrum between 0 and 220 ppm. The seven regions typically considered are: 0-45 ppm = alkyl C (comprising lipids, waxes, resins, suberin); 45-60 ppm = methoxyl and N-alkyl C (comprising the methoxyl group of guaiacyl and the two methoxyl groups of syringyl lignin moieties at ~ 56 ppm); 60-90 ppm = O-alkyl C (from carbohydrates, chiefly cellulose and hemicellulose); 90-110 ppm = di-O-alkyl C; 110-140 ppm = H- and C-substituted aromatic C; 140-160 ppm = O-substituted aromatic C (mainly ascribable to lignin structures, tannins, polyphenols); 160-190 ppm = carboxyl C (esters, acids and amides). No significant signal in the 190-220 ppm region from carbonyl of aldehydes and ketones was detected. In a few spectra there was a small signal at ~ 250 ppm ascribed to aromatic spinning side bands; however, it was neglected in the integration procedure because of its very low intensity. Although CPMAS NMR spectra are not *per se* quantitative (Berns and Conte, 2011), the relative spectral contributions can be used for

comparative purposes. For the assignment of the single resonance lines to specific C moieties we referred to the spectral editing by Forte et al. (2006) and Keeler et al. (2006).

2.5 ¹⁴C measurements and turnover time of SOM

The bulk soil and the soil fractions from each depth interval were analysed for their ¹⁴C concentration by an Accelerator Mass Spectrometer (AMS) at the Centre for Isotopic Research on Cultural and Environmental heritage (CIRCE) of the University of Campania "Luigi Vanvitelli", Caserta, Italy. A detailed description of the methodology used for sample preparation and measurement can be found in Marzaioli et al. (2008) and Terrasi et al. (2008). Measured radiocarbon ratios were expressed in percent Modern Carbon (pMC) according to Stuiver and Polach (1977). Values of pMC greater than 97.5 indicate a substantial presence in the sample of ¹⁴C produced by nuclear weapons testing during the 1950s ("bomb C"); by contrast, pMC values lower than 97.5 indicated that the sample has no incorporated, or only slightly, amounts of "bomb C".

The TT of SOM was determined from the ¹⁴C concentrations, using the time-dependent steady-state (TDSS) model proposed by Gaudinski et al. (2000). This model bases on important assumptions: a) being at the steady state, *i.e.* the situation in which C inputs and outputs are equivalent; b) the ¹⁴C signature of SOM at any time strictly depends on the ¹⁴C signatures of the atmosphere in previous years; c) the time-lag between the ¹⁴C value of the atmosphere and new inputs to the litter layer and other soil pools is 3 years, because deciduous trees shed leaves each year, while evergreen trees shed their leaves every two to five years; d) all C atoms in a given pool have the same probability of leaving that pool, which implies normal distribution of TT's, and; e) every pool is homogenous in terms of ¹⁴C signature. These assumptions are better met by SOM fractions than the bulk SOM, because the latter has more heterogeneous composition (McFarlane et al., 2013). It is worth to note that, at the steady state, TT coincides with the mean residence time (MRT) and the ¹⁴C age.

An atmospheric radiocarbon dataset (Hua et al., 2013) of the bomb-spike period (1950-2010), for the northern hemisphere (NH3 zone), was used annually averaging all available data to smooth the

seasonal variability of atmospheric ^{14}C . Data gap filling and extrapolation from 2010 to 2011 for the NH3 zone was performed using the best fitting function. A prebomb dataset for the NH3 zone was obtained from the INTCAL 09 (Reimer et al., 2009). For the TDSS modelling of SOM, each depth interval was assumed to have reached the steady state in 1900 with an initial radiocarbon signature as in Wang et al. (1996).

Radiocarbon concentration on the bomb-spike curve results in two possible TT's on the opposite sides of the ^{14}C peak (Marín-Spiotta et al., 2008). In our case, this occurred only in the 0-5 cm layer, in both bulk soil and soil fractions. We identified the more likely solution based on the aboveground litterfall rates and the C stock of that specific soil layer, according to McFarlane et al. (2013) and Marin-Spiotta et al. (2008).

2.6 Statistics

Statistical significance of differences in C concentrations and stocks in the selected soil layers were determined by analysis of variance (ANOVA). When significant interaction effects were observed, a multiple comparison test (Tukey) was performed. Statistical significance for ANOVA and Tukey test were assessed at a 95% confidence level ($p < 0.05$). Differences between soil fractions were checked by a *t*-test ($p < 0.05$). All statistical analyses were performed using the R software (R Core Team, 2016).

3. Results

3.1 X-Ray diffractometry

The XRD investigation revealed that the bulk soil consisted of quartz, clay minerals, and lower amounts of goethite/hematite and feldspars throughout the profile (Fig. 1). There were no major differences in mineralogical assemblage between both depth intervals (0-5, 5-15, 15-30, and 30-50 cm) and size fractions (<0.5 mm and 0.5-2.0 mm). The spectra of the two MA and MN fine fractions from 30-50 cm, which are representative of the corresponding samples from the rest of the

soil profile, are displayed in Fig. 2. The clay fraction from the same depth almost totally consisted of kaolinite with ancillary illite, as confirmed by a diagnostic treatment at 550 °C for 4 hours that removed all peaks typical of kaolinite. The MA and NM fractions from each soil layer differed for both kaolinite and goethite/hematite. The RIR-based amounts of kaolinite in the MA and NM fractions from the 30-50 cm depth were 27% and 8%, respectively. In particular, the intensity of the kaolinite (001) reflection ($d_{\text{spacing}} = 0.72$ nm) was approximately three times higher in the MA fraction than in the NM one (Fig. 2), a proportion that was observed in all samples.

The dissolution by dithionite–citrate–bicarbonate revealed substantially higher concentrations of free iron in the magnetic fractions than in the non-magnetic ones, with the single exception of the finer fraction from the 0-5 cm depth (Table 1). This iron is in the form of both crystalline and non-crystalline oxides, as well as other possible ancillary Fe species, such as soluble Fe, exchangeable Fe, and Fe bound to organic matter. Moreover, there is a general, although slight, increasing depth-trend of DCB-extractable Fe. The iron dissolved by the acid ammonium oxalate is very little and did not show any clear depth-trend or unambiguous difference between depth intervals, and/or fractions with different size or MS (Table 1).

3.2 C concentrations and stocks

The C concentration in the bulk soil drastically decreased from the top 5 cm of soil to the deeper depth intervals, which did not show significant differences between each other (Table 2). In terms of soil organic carbon (SOC) stock, the 0-5 cm layer contained 30.1 ± 3.5 Mg C ha⁻¹, which is about 40% of the total SOC present in the 0-50 cm compartment of mineral soil (Table 2).

Looking at the soil fractions, in the 0-5 cm interval, the fine MA fraction was significantly richer in C than the other three fractions (Table 3). At greater depth, the MA fractions were always significantly richer in C than the corresponding NM ones, except in the 30-50 cm depth interval, while no significant differences were observed between the two MA size fractions and between the two NM ones (Table 3).

3.3 SOM fractions composition

The C concentrations in the soil fractions after HF treatment are shown in Table S1. It is known that the HF treatment mainly removes the mineral phase inducing also some C loss, although unselective (Gonçalves et al., 2003; Skjemstad et al., 1994). Nonetheless, the two types of magnetic fractions behaved differently: the MA fractions experienced an increase in C concentration down to 15 cm, whereas the NM ones from all depth intervals suffered a decrease in C concentration (Table S1). Evidently the treatment caused a larger removal of the mineral phase in the MA fractions or, alternatively, of the organic matter in the NM ones.

The NMR spectra of soil fractions from the 0-5 cm and 5-15 cm depth intervals are displayed in Fig. 3, and the relative intensities of their chemical shift regions are shown in Table 4. Soil samples deeper than 15 cm provided so low quality NMR spectra (most probably due to insufficient C) that they are neither shown nor discussed. The patterns of the 0-5 cm soil layer showed dominant signals centred at 30 and 72 ppm, in the alkyl C and O-alkyl C regions, respectively. The former peak belonged to methylene carbons in alkyl chains and methyl carbons of acetyl groups in aliphatic structures, while the peak at 72 ppm is typically associated to secondary carbinol carbons, including those of cellulose and hemicellulose. A peak centered in the O-alkyl C region at 63 ppm – generally assigned to C6 carbons (-CH₂-OH) of the glucose unit in cellulose – and one in the di-O-alkyl region at 105 ppm – ascribable to anomeric carbon (O-C-O) of the glucose in cellulose – were also present. Major differences between the spectra were observed in the aromatic C region. Here, dominant signals occurred at 115, 130 and 150 ppm, all of them ascribable to lignin moieties, although the one at 130 ppm probably revealed some charred materials as well. The sharp peak at 175 ppm was due to carboxyl groups and, possibly, to amides and polypeptides. Overall, the NM fractions showed higher contribution from aromatic C and more distinct peaks than the MA ones (Fig. 3). Although with lower signal-to-noise ratio (as expected considering the paucity in organic C), the spectra of the 5-15 cm depth differed little from those of the overlying soil in terms of

relative intensities of the chemical shift regions (Table 4), and the major differences between the spectra of this soil layer were the lower intensity of the aromatic and carboxyl signals in the MA <0.5 mm fractions, and the higher alkyl C contribution, mainly at the expense of the O-alkyl C, in the NM <0.5 mm fractions.

3.4 ¹⁴C concentration and turnover time of SOM in bulk soil and fractions

The ¹⁴C concentration of the bulk soil progressively decreased with increasing depth (Table 5), from a modern signature (109.3 pMC) in the 0-5 cm layer to a pMC value of 87.2 in the 30-50 cm one. Below 5 cm depth, the influence of C synthesized after the 1950's was minor.

No noteworthy differences in ¹⁴C concentration in the different SOM fractions from the 0-5 cm depth interval were observed, while in the underlying 5-15 cm one just the fine NM fraction showed a pre-bomb signature (Table 5). Below 5 cm depth, the <0.5 mm MA fraction was richer in ¹⁴C than the fine NM one, while the MA and NM fractions of the coarser material (0.5-2.0 mm) substantially differed only in the 30-50 cm depth interval.

The TT of the bulk SOM increased progressively with depth, from 10 years in the top 0-5 cm layer to almost 1500 years in the deepest 30-50 cm one (Table 5). The MA and NM fractions from 0-5 cm did not show significant differences in terms of TT, all ranging between 7 and 11 years. Differences were evident between the fine fractions in the 5-15 cm soil layer – 197 years for MA and 943 years for NM – while both coarse fractions showed a TT of 327 years. The same trend was observed at greater depth, where the fine MA fraction showed the shortest TT, the fine NM fraction the longest TT, and the coarse fractions intermediate TTs (Table 5).

4. Discussion

4.1 Mineralogical assemblage and SOM chemical structure in soil fractions

The application of HGMS allowed the separation of soil fractions with distinct mineralogical assemblages and organic pools. As revealed by the XRD investigation, the minerals in this highly

altered soil are few: quartz, kaolinite, illite, and iron oxides, the latter identified as a goethite/hematite phase by both XRD and selective dissolutions. Actually, a substantial amount of iron was recovered only by the DCB treatment, which is able to dissolve both crystalline oxides (such as goethite and hematite) and the non-crystalline ones. On the contrary, acid ammonium oxalate succeeded in dissolving very low amounts of Fe, which means a minor occurrence of Fe forms prone to this treatment, such as non-crystalline oxides, or partly prone, such as the crystalline oxides magnetite and maghemite. Being our samples unground, the real amount of oxalate-extractable Fe could be underestimated in the 0.5-2.0 mm fraction (Neary and Barnes, 1993). Nevertheless, this can not account for otherwise abundant magnetite and maghemite. Kaolinite and iron oxides were significantly more abundant in the MA fractions (Fig. 2), where they were the most probable cause of MS. In reality, kaolinite is a low-charged and diamagnetic (i.e. repelled by a magnetic field) 1:1 phyllosilicate, but it may intimately coexist with the antiferromagnetic goethite and hematite, so sharing their moderate MS (Schroeder et al., 1998).

At all depths, the MA fraction showed higher C content than the NM one, hence suggesting some positive relation between magnetic minerals and SOM. A major contribution in this regard is most likely given by the iron oxides, which actually are strong binding partners of organic matter because of their surface configuration (Shang and Tiessen, 1997). It cannot be excluded that the MS per se provide oxides with some affinity for some organic compounds or, as supported by Wilson et al. (2008), for soil biota.

In terms of SOM quality, the MA fractions had larger contributions from relatively labile C forms, such as polysaccharides or peptides, while the NM fractions were richer in aromatic C, from lignin in particulate organic matter or, less probably, humic substances and charcoal. Structural differences of SOM between fractions were particularly evident in the 0-5 cm soil layer, where most of SOM was stored. In this layer, the incorporation of roots residues and aboveground litter could happen more than elsewhere, apparently preferentially in the non-magnetic fraction (Table 4), leading to hypothesize a role of minerals as driving factor in controlling SOM retention and

decomposition. Actually, a particular affinity of polysaccharides, lipids, and readily decomposable sugars with kaolinite was described in some tropical soils by Wattel-Koekkoek et al. (2001).

4.2 Turnover time of SOM in fractions

The two-step soil fractionation, the first on a size basis and the second on a MS basis, enabled us to distinguish C pools with different TT's. In fact, at all depths, SOM in the fine MA fraction showed shorter TT than SOM in the other fractions, especially the fine NM fraction. In particular, in the 5-15 cm depth interval, the TT of SOM associated with the fine NM fraction was on average almost 1,000 years, hence five times longer than that of the SOM of the fine MA fraction. Nevertheless, the TT of the fine MA fraction is two times the ¹⁴C age – which at steady state is equivalent to TT – found by Shang and Tiessen (1997) in the MA fraction from the topsoil of a Brazilian Oxisol, about 100 years. This finding suggests that kaolinite – which was confined in the MA fractions – played some role in binding SOM, as suggested by the preferential association of SOM with the MA fractions. On the other hand, Wattel-Koekkoek et al. (2003) reported a TT of 357 years for the SOM associated with kaolinite in the surface horizon of an African tropical soil, advancing some significant role of this low-charged mineral in protecting SOM from decay. A significant role of kaolinite in this regards, *per se* or bound to iron oxides, was also demonstrated by Wiseman and Püttmann (2006) in European soils experiencing temperate oceanic climate.

The TT's of SOM we observed in the Ankasa forest were similar to those from other Oxisols in other African tropical forests in Kenya (Chiti et al., 2018) and Gabon (Chiti et al., 2017). Overall, the long TT demonstrates the considerable potential of these highly altered soils to stabilize C. A previous study focusing on pedogenic horizons and bulk soil measurements, performed at the same site by Chiti et al. (2010), revealed that some bomb C was present in the Bo1 horizon, which comprises the 5-15, 15-30, and 30-50 cm depth intervals considered in this study. Here, we assessed that only the uppermost portion of the Bo1 horizon, i.e. the 5-15 cm depth interval, actually contained significant amounts of bomb C, and, furthermore, that the fine NM fraction was only

marginally or not at all influenced by bomb C. Below 15 cm depth, whether bomb C is present its amount can be considered minor and/or hidden by ancient C. These facts suggest that the top 15 cm are the only soil compartment where SOM dynamics are actually influenced by the standing vegetation and, when the C is transported deeper it can remain in soil for millennia.

Studies on the characterization of the organic matter associated with different soil fractions separated by HGMS are few. The ones by Shang and Tiessen (1997, 2000) only take into account the clay fraction, concluding that the richer in Fe oxides this fraction is, the more stable is the SOM it comprises. Results from this study also indicated that Fe oxides, mainly present in the fine MA fraction, apparently promote both sequestration and stabilization of SOM, despite also the NM fraction is able to stabilize SOM.

The findings of this work, in particular the significant differences in TT of the SOM occurring in soil fractions of different size and MS, support the rationality of fractionating the investigated soil on the basis of these properties. Nevertheless, to clarify whether such a soil fractionation procedure can be suitable for the separation of different SOM fractions it would be necessary to apply the method to a wider range of soils characterized by different properties.

5. Conclusions

High Gradient Magnetic Separation was successfully used in this work to obtain SOM fractions with different composition and TT from a forest soil of Ghana. Overall, the soil fraction susceptible to magnetism, because of the presence of Fe-oxides hematite and/or goethite, retained more organic matter than the magnetically inert one. In spite of such a higher affinity, the magnetic fraction of soil showed an organic pool with shorter TT than the one associated with the non-magnetic fraction; the latter, in fact, appeared to be fairly stable in the entire profile. Differences in composition and TT of SOM in soil fractions with different MS could promote or be a consequence of the preferential microbial colonisation of magnetic minerals in soil described by other authors, although further investigation is needed in this regard.

Although the findings of this study confirm the importance of the composition of the inorganic matrix in controlling the sequestration and the TT of organic matter in soil, a general conclusion on a wider application of this methodology cannot be derived and the findings should only be treated as results from a case study.

Acknowledgements

This work benefited of the financial contribution of the “ERC Africa GHG project” (# n° 037132). The authors gratefully acknowledge the Ankasa park manager, C. Balangtaa, the park rangers, and J. J. Mensah for their precious support during the sampling campaign.

References

- Achard, F., Beuchle, R., Mayaux, P., Stibig, H.J., Bodart, C., Brink, A., Carboni, S., Desclée, B., Donnay, F., Eva, H.D., Lupi, A., Rasi, R., Seliger, R., Simonetti, D., 2014. Determination of tropical deforestation rates and related carbon losses from 1990 to 2010. *Glob. Change Biol.* 20, 2540–2554.
- Ahn, P.M., 1961., Soils of the Lower Tano Basin, South-Western Ghana. Ministry of Food and Agriculture, Scientific Services Division, Soil and Land-use Survey Branch, Kumasi. Available at: http://library.wur.nl/isric/fulltext/isricu_i00002533_001.pdf [Accessed May 16th, 2018]
- Berenguer, E., Ferreira, J., Gardner, T.A. et al., 2014. A large-scale field assessment of C stocks in human-modified tropical forests. *Glob. Change Biol.* 20, 3713–3726.
- Berns,, A.E., Conte, P., 2011. Effect of ramp size and sample spinning speed on CPMAS ¹³C NMR spectra of soil organic matter. *Org. Geochem.* 42, 926–935.
- Blakemore, L.C., Searle, P.L., Daly, B.K., 1987. Acid oxalate-extractable iron, aluminium and silicon. Methods for Chemical Analysis of Soils, New Zealand Soil Bureau Scientific Report n. 80, Lower Hutt, NZ.

- Brindley, G.W., Brown, G., 1980. Crystal Structures of Clay Minerals and their X-ray Identification. Mineralogical Society, Monograph No. 5, London.
- Certini, G., Scalenghe, R., Woods, W.W., 2013. The impact of warfare on the soil environment. *Earth-Sci. Rev.* 127, 1–15.
- Certini, G., Agnelli, A., Corti, G., Capperucci, A. 2004. Composition and mean residence time of molecular weight fractions of organic matter extracted from two soils under different forest species. *Biogeochemistry* 71, 299–316.
- Chiti, T., Díaz-Pinés, E., Butterbach-Bahl, K., Marzaioli, F., Valentini R., 2018. Soil organic carbon changes following degradation and conversion to cypress and tea plantations in a tropical mountain forest of Kenya. *Plant Soil* 422, 527–539.
- Chiti, T., Mihindou, V., Jeffery, K.J., Mahli, Y., Oliveira, F., White, L.J.T., Valentini, R. 2017. Impact of woody encroachment on soil organic carbon storage in the Lopè National Park, Gabon. *Biotropica* 49, 9–12.
- Chiti, T., Perugini, L., Vespertino, D., Valentini, R., 2016. Effect of selective logging on soil organic carbon dynamics in tropical forests in Central and western Africa. *Plant Soil* 399, 283–294.
- Chiti, T., Grieco, E., Perugini, L., Rey, A., Valentini, R., 2014. Effect of the replacement of tropical tree plantations on soil organic carbon levels in the Jomoro district, Ghana. *Plant Soil* 375, 47–59.
- Chiti, T., Neubert, R.E.M., Janssens, I.A., Curiel Yuste, J., Sirignano, C., Certini, G., 2011. Radiocarbon based assessment of soil organic carbon contribution to soil respiration in a pine stand of the Campine region, Belgium. *Plant Soil* 344, 273–282.
- Chiti T., Certini G., Grieco E., Valentini R., 2010. The role of soil in storing carbon in tropical rainforests: the case of Ankasa park, Ghana. *Plant Soil* 331, 453–461.
- Colombo, C., di Iorio, E., Liu, Q., Jiang, Z., Barrón, V., 2017. Iron oxide nanoparticles in soils: Environmental and agronomic importance. *J. Nanosci. Nanotech.* 17, 4449–4460.

- Fassbinder, J.W.E., Stanjek, H., Vali, H., 1990. Occurrence of magnetic bacteria in soil. *Nature* 343, 161–163.
- Forte, C., Piazzzi, A., Pizzanelli, S., Certini, G., 2006. CP MAS ^{13}C spectral editing and relative quantitation of a bulk soil sample. *Solid State Nucl. Magn.* 30, 81–88.
- Gaudinski, J.B., Trumbore, S.E., Davidson, E.A., Zheng, S.H., 2000. Soil carbon cycling in a temperate forest: radiocarbon based estimates of residence times, sequestration rates and partitioning of fluxes. *Biogeochemistry* 51, 33–69.
- Gonçalves, C.N., Dalmolin, R.S.D., Dick, D.P., Knicker, H., Klamt, E., Kögel-Knabner, I., 2003. The effect of 10% HF treatment on the resolution of CPMAS C-13 NMR spectra and on the quality of organic matter in Ferralsols. *Geoderma* 116, 373–392.
- Grace, J., Mitchard, E., Gloor, E., 2014. Perturbations in the carbon budget of the tropics. *Glob. Change. Biol.* 20, 3238–3255.
- Han, L., Sun, K., Jin, J., Xing, B., 2016. Some concepts of soil organic carbon characteristics and mineral interaction from a review of literature. *Soil Biol. Biochem.* 94, 107–121.
- Hua, Q., Barbetti, M., Rakowski, A., 2013. Atmospheric radiocarbon for the period 1950-2010. *Radiocarbon* 55, 2059–2072.
- Igel, J., Preetz, H., Altfelder, S., 2012. Magnetic viscosity of tropical soils: classification and prediction as an aid for landmine detection. *Geophys. J. Int.* 190, 843–855.
- Kaiser, K., Eusterhues, K., Rumpel, C., Guggenberger G., Kögel-Knabner I., 2002. Stabilization of organic matter by soil minerals—investigations of density and particle-size fractions from two acid forest soils. *J. Plant. Nutr. Soil. Sci.* 165, 451–459.
- Kaiser, M., Ellerbrock, R.H., 2005. Functional characterization of soil organic matter fractions different in solubility originating from a longterm field experiment. *Geoderma* 127, 196–206.
- Keeler, C., Kelly E.F., Maciel, G.E., 2006. Chemical-structural information from solid-state ^{13}C NMR studies of a suite of humic materials from a lower montane forest soil, Colorado, USA. *Geoderma* 130, 124–140.

- Marín-Spiotta E., Swanston C.W., Torn M.S., Silver W.L., Burton S.D., 2008. Chemical and mineral control of soil carbon turnover in abandoned tropical pastures. *Geoderma* 143, 49–62.
- Marzaioli, F., Borriello, G., Passariello, I., Lubritto, C., de Cesare, N., D'Onofrio, A., Terrasi, F., 2008. Zinc reduction as an alternative method for AMS radiocarbon dating: Process optimization at CIRCE. *Radiocarbon* 50, 139–149.
- McFarlane, K.J., Torn, M.S., Hanson, P.J., Porras, R.C., Swanston, C.W., Callaham Jr, M.A., Guilderson, T.P., 2013. Comparison of soil organic matter dynamics at five temperate deciduous forests with physical fractionation and radiocarbon measurements. *Biogeochemistry* 112, 457–476.
- McKeague, J.A., Day, J.H., 1966. Dithionite- and oxalate-extractable Fe and Al as aids in differentiating various classes of soils. *Can. J. Soil Sci.* 46, 13–22.
- Mehra, O. P., Jackson, M. L., 1960. Iron Oxide Removal from Soils and Clay by a Dithionite-Citrate System Buffered with Sodium Bicarbonate. *Clays and Clay Minerals* 7, 317–327.
- Miles, L., Kapos, V., 2008. Reducing greenhouse gas emissions from deforestation and forest degradation: global land-use implications. *Science* 320, 1454–1455.
- Neary, A.J., Barnes, S.R., 1993. The effect of sample grinding on extractable iron and aluminum in soils. *Can. J. Soil Sci.* 73, 73–80.
- Preetz, H., Igel, J., Hannam, J.A., Stadler, S., 2017. Relationship between magnetic properties and reddening of tropical soils as indicators of weathering. *Geoderma* 303, 143–149.
- R Core Team, 2016. R: A language and environment for statistical computing. R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria. URL <https://www.R-project.org/>
- Reimer, P.J., Baillie, M.G.L., Bard, E., et al., 2009. IntCal09 and Marine09 radiocarbon age calibration curves, 0-50,000 years CAL BP. *Radiocarbon* 51, 1111–1150.
- Russell, J.D., Birnie A., Fraser, A.R., 1984. High-gradient magnetic separation (HGMS) in soil clay mineral studies. *Clay Miner.* 19, 771–778.

- Saner, P., Loh, Y.Y., Ong, R.C., Hector, A., 2012. Carbon stocks and fluxes in tropical lowland dipterocarp rainforests in Sabah, Malaysian Borneo. *PLoS ONE* 7, e29642.
- Schroeder, P.A., Pruett R. J., Hurst V.J., 1998. Effects of secondary iron phases on kaolinite ^{27}Al MAS NMR spectra. *Clay Clay Min.* 46, 429–435.
- Shang, C., Tiessen, H., 1997. Organic matter lability in a tropical oxisol: evidence from shifting cultivation, chemical oxidation, particle size, density and magnetic fractionations. *Soil Sci.* 162, 795–807.
- Shang, C., Tiessen, H., 2000. Organic carbon turnover and carbon-13 natural abundance in organo–mineral fractions of a tropical dry forest soil under cultivation. *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. J.* 65, 2149–2155.
- Singer, M.J., Fine, P., 1989. Pedogenic factors affecting magnetic susceptibility on Northern California soils. *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. J.* 53, 1119–1127.
- Skjemstad, J.O., Clarke, P., Taylor, J.A., Oades, J.M., Newman, R.H., 1994. The removal of magnetic materials from surface soils. A solid-state ^{13}C CP/MAS NMR study. *Aust. J. Soil. Res.* 32, 1215–1229.
- Soil Survey Staff, 2014. *Keys to Soil Taxonomy*, 12th ed. USDA-NRCS, Washington, DC.
- Stuiver, M., Polach, H.A., 1977. Discussion: Reporting of ^{14}C data. *Radiocarbon* 19, 355–363.
- Tardy, Y., 1997. *Petrology of Laterites and Tropical Soils*. A.A. Balkema, Rotterdam.
- Terrasi, F., De Cesare, N., D'Onofrio, A., Lubritto, C., Marzaioli, F., Passariello, I., Rogalla, D., Sabbarese, C., Borriello, G., Casa, G., Palmieri, A., 2008. High precision ^{14}C AMS at CIRCE. *Nucl. Instrum. Meth. B* 266, 2221–2224.
- Throop, H.L., Lajtha, K., Kramer, M., 2013. Density fractionation and ^{13}C reveal changes in soil carbon following woody encroachment in a desert ecosystem. *Biogeochemistry* 112, 409–422.
- Torn, M.S., Swanston, C.W., Castanha, C., Trumbore, S.E., 2009. Storage and turnover of organic matter in soil, in: Senesi, N., Xing, B., Huang, P.M (Eds), *Biophysico-chemical processes*

- involving natural non living organic matter in environmental systems, Wiley, Hoboken, pp. 219–272.
- Torn, M.S., Trumbore, S.E., Chadwick, O.A., Vitousek, P.M., Hendricks, D.M., 1997. Mineral control of soil organic carbon storage and turnover. *Nature* 389, 170–173.
- Trumbore, S., 2009. Radiocarbon and soil carbon dynamics. *Annu. Rev. Earth. Pl. Sc.* 37, 47–66.
- Vaglio Laurin, G., Hawthorne, W.D., Chiti, T., Di Paola, A., Cazzolla Gatti, R., Marconi, S., Noce, S., Grieco, E., Pirotti, F., Valentini, R., 2016. Does degradation from selective logging and illegal activities differently impact forest resources? A case study in Ghana. *iForest* 9, 354–362.
- Valentini, R., Arneeth, A., Bombelli, A. et al., 2014. A full greenhouse gases budget of Africa: synthesis, uncertainties, and vulnerabilities. *Biogeosciences* 11, 381–407.
- van Oorschot, I.H.M., Dekkers, M.J., 2001. Selective dissolution of magnetic iron oxides in the acid–ammonium oxalate/ferrous iron extraction method—I. Synthetic samples. *Geophys. J. Int.* 145, 740–748.
- von Lützow, M., Kögel-Knabner, I., Ekschmitt, K., Flessa, H., Guggenberger, G., Matzner, E., Marschner, B., 2007. SOM fractionation methods: Relevance to functional pools and to stabilization mechanisms. *Soil Biol. Biochem.* 39, 2183–2207.
- Wang, Y., Amundson, R., Trumbore, S.E., 1996. Radiocarbon dating of soil organic matter. *Quaternary Research* 45, 282–288.
- Wattel-Koekkoek, E.J.W., van Genuchten, P.P.L., Buurman, P., van Lagen, B., 2001. Amount and composition of clay-associated soil organic matter in a range of kaolinitic and smectitic soils. *Geoderma* 99, 27–49.
- Wattel-Koekkoek, E.J.W., Buurman, P., van der Plicht, J., Wattel, E., van Breemen, N. 2003. Mean residence time of soil organic matter associated with kaolinite and smectite. *Eur. J. Soil. Sci.* 54, 269–278.

Wilson, M.J., Certini, G., Campbell, C.D., Anderson, I.C., Hillier, S., 2008. Does the preferential microbial colonisation of ferromagnesian minerals affect mineral weathering in soil? *Naturwissenschaften* 95, 851–858.

Wiseman, C.L.S., Püttmann, W., 2006. Interactions between mineral phases in the preservation of soil organic matter. *Geoderma* 134, 109–118.

Captions

Table 1 – Iron (Fe) extracted by acid oxalate and dithionite-citrate-bicarbonate (DCB) from soil fractions with different size and/or magnetic susceptibility. MA = magnetic fraction; NM = non-magnetic fraction.

Table 2 – Bulk density, SOC concentration, and SOC stock in the bulk soil from different depth intervals. Different letters within a column indicate significant differences between soil layers (n=6; ANOVA, $p < 0.05$).

Table 3 – SOC concentration and standard deviation of the magnetic and non-magnetic fractions (n=3 per soil layer). Numbers within brackets are the percent contribution of each fraction to total weight of the bulk sample. Different letters within a single row indicate significant differences between soil fractions (t -test; $p < 0.05$).

Table 4 – Percent contribution of the seven main chemical-shift regions to the total NMR signal spectral area of the 0-5 cm and 5-15 cm depth intervals. MA is for “magnetic”, NM for “non-magnetic”. Maximum experimental error is 10%.

Table 5 – ^{14}C concentration (expressed as percent modern carbon, pMC), measurement error (σ), and turnover time (TT) of the bulk soil and soil fractions calculated by the time dependent steady state (TDSS) model and based on atmospheric ^{14}C concentrations of the northern hemisphere (NH3 zone).

Figure 1 – XRD spectra of the bulk soil from different depth intervals. K=kaolinite; I=illite; F=feldspars; G=goethite; H=hematite; Q=quartz.

Figure 2 – XRD spectra of the magnetic (MA) and non-magnetic (NM) fine fractions (<0.5 mm) from the 30-50 cm soil layer. Inset is a particular of the XRD spectra of the separated clay mineral fraction after heating to 500 °C. K=kaolinite; I=illite; F=feldspars; G=goethite; H=hematite; Q=quartz.

Figure 3 – ^{13}C CPMAS NMR spectra of the magnetic (MA) and non-magnetic (NM) soil fractions from the 0-5 cm and 5-15 cm depth intervals.

Figure S1 – Scheme of the working principle of the High Gradient Magnetic Separator.

Figure S2 – Percent contribution, on a weight basis, of the magnetic fractions to the bulk soil applying different amperages to the magnet. Error bars are standard deviations of $n=3$.

Table S1 – SOC concentration and standard deviation in the magnetic (MA) and non-magnetic (NM) fractions after the HF treatment necessary for the NMR analysis ($n=3$ per soil layer). n.a. = not applicable. In brackets is report the percentage of dry matter loss during the HF treatment.

APPENDIX A – Supplementary Material

Figure S1 - Scheme of the working principle of the High Gradient Magnetic Separator.

Figure S2 - Percent contribution, on weight basis, of the magnetic fractions to the bulk soil applying different amperages to the magnet. Error bars are standard deviations of $n=3$.

Table S1 - SOC concentration and standard deviation in the magnetic and non-magnetic fractions after the HF treatment necessary for the NMR analysis (n=3 per soil layer). n.a. = not applicable. In brackets is report the percentage of dry matter loss during the HF treatment.

Depth	Magnetic fractions		Non magnetic fractions	
	<0.5 mm	0.5-2.0 mm	<0.5 mm	0.5-2.0 mm
cm	g C kg ⁻¹	g C kg ⁻¹	g C kg ⁻¹	g C kg ⁻¹
0-5	247.7 ± 21.4 (29)	188.6 ± 13.2 (27)	46.7 ± 22.8 (63)	33.6 ± 11.5 (67)
5-15	23.9 ± 4.7 (31)	15.5 ± 5.3 (59)	2.0 ± 1.1 (69)	3.5 ± 1.2 (72)
15-30	13.3 ± 4.3 (57)	9.4 ± 3.2 (61)	1.7 ± 0.8 (77)	0.9 ± 0.2 (75)
30-50	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.